

DNA barcoding reveals genetic divergence and phylogenetic relationships of *Scymnus* species (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) from Uzbekistan

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Abstract. Ladybird beetles of the genus *Scymnus* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) are key predators in agroecosystems, yet species-level identification remains challenging due to high morphological similarity among closely related taxa. Molecular data for Central Asian populations are scarce, limiting regional representation in global barcode libraries. Here, we analyzed mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) sequences to investigate phylogenetic relationships and genetic divergence of four *Scymnus* species from Uzbekistan (*S. rubromaculatus*, *S. frontalis*, *S. subvillosus*, and *S. apetzi*). A total of 32 mitochondrial COI sequences (503 bp), including 16 newly generated sequences from Uzbekistan and 16 sequences retrieved from GenBank, were analyzed. Phylogenetic reconstruction using Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian Inference recovered all four species as well-supported monophyletic clades. Intraspecific divergence was low in *S. rubromaculatus* (K2P = 0.00203), *S. frontalis* (0.00717), and *S. apetzi* (0.01087), whereas *S. subvillosus* showed comparatively higher variation (0.05558), indicating potential geographic structuring. Interspecific divergence ranged from 0.157 to 0.169, revealing a clear barcode gap. These findings confirm the reliability of COI barcoding for species delimitation within *Scymnus* and provide the first molecular reference dataset for *Scymnus* species from Uzbekistan, expanding the barcode representation of Central Asian Coccinellidae.

Keywords: *Scymnus*; DNA barcoding; mitochondrial COI; phylogenetic analysis; Coccinellidae; Uzbekistan

Running title: DNA barcoding of *Scymnus* species

INTRODUCTION

Ladybird beetles (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) are among the most important predatory insect groups in terrestrial ecosystems and contribute substantially to the

natural regulation of agricultural pests. Most species prey on aphids, scale insects, mites, and other soft-bodied arthropods, thereby reducing pest abundance in both cultivated and natural habitats (Bianchi et al., 2013). Owing to their ecological and economic importance, coccinellids have been widely investigated in studies of biodiversity, trophic interactions, and biological control. Their effectiveness as natural enemies has also increased interest in understanding species diversity, ecological specialization, and evolutionary relationships within the family.

Despite extensive ecological research, species delimitation within several coccinellid groups remains problematic because of high morphological similarity among closely related taxa. This challenge is particularly evident in small-bodied genera, where diagnostic characters such as coloration, pubescence, elytral markings, and body shape often overlap among species (Huang et al., 2020; Peng et al., 2025). The genus *Scymnus* Kugelann, 1794 represents one of the most taxonomically complex groups within Coccinellidae. Many species exhibit conservative external morphology and limited diagnostic differentiation, increasing the risk of misidentification when only morphological characters are used (Iqbal et al., 2024; Peng et al., 2025). In addition, variation associated with sex, developmental stage, or geographic population may further obscure species boundaries. These limitations highlight the need for complementary molecular approaches in the taxonomy of *Scymnus*.

Mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) has become one of the most widely used molecular markers for insect identification and phylogenetic studies. COI-based DNA barcoding has proven effective for distinguishing closely related taxa, testing species monophyly, detecting cryptic diversity, and assessing genetic differentiation among populations (Hebert & Gregory, 2005; Valentini et al., 2009). In Coccinellidae, COI datasets have substantially improved species-level resolution and clarified phylogenetic relationships across multiple genera (Huang et al., 2020; Iqbal et al., 2024). Although molecular studies of *Scymnus* have increased in recent years, available barcode data are still concentrated mainly in Europe, China, Pakistan, and other parts of East and South Asia (Elekcioğlu, 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Peng et al., 2025). In contrast, Central Asian populations remain poorly represented in global genetic databases.

Uzbekistan occupies a biogeographically important position between arid lowlands, desert ecosystems, foothill zones, and mountain systems, creating diverse ecological conditions for insect assemblages. Species of *Scymnus* are widespread in these habitats and play an important role in regulating pest populations in alfalfa fields, orchards, and vegetable agroecosystems. Among them, *Scymnus rubromaculatus*, *S. frontalis*, *S. subvillosus*, and *S. apetzi* are frequently encountered

and are considered ecologically significant predators in agricultural landscapes. However, previous studies from Uzbekistan and neighboring regions have focused mainly on faunistic records, distributional observations, and morphological descriptions, whereas molecular evidence remains extremely limited (Gafurova et al., 2025). As a result, phylogenetic relationships, genetic divergence, and population-level variation within regional *Scymnus* taxa remain insufficiently understood.

The absence of representative COI datasets from Central Asia limits accurate species identification and reduces the phylogeographic resolution of Palearctic *Scymnus* populations. This gap also constrains comparative biodiversity studies and weakens the development of molecular reference libraries for ecologically important predatory beetles. Expanding barcode coverage for Central Asian taxa is therefore important not only for regional taxonomy, but also for broader studies of evolutionary diversity and biological control.

The present study investigates mitochondrial COI sequences of four *Scymnus* species collected from Uzbekistan in order to evaluate their genetic divergence and phylogenetic relationships. Specifically, the study aims to: (i) assess species-level monophyly using COI barcodes, (ii) compare intra- and interspecific genetic divergence patterns, and (iii) evaluate the effectiveness of COI sequences for delimiting morphologically similar *Scymnus* species. We further test whether geographically sampled populations of *S. subvillosus* exhibit comparatively elevated intraspecific divergence relative to the other examined taxa. The resulting dataset provides the first COI-based molecular reference framework for these *Scymnus* species in Uzbekistan and contributes to the growing barcode representation of Central Asian Coccinellidae.

This study provides the first publicly documented COI barcode framework for *Scymnus* species from Uzbekistan and one of the first regional molecular datasets for Central Asian Scymnini.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling and specimen collection

This study examined four species of the genus *Scymnus* collected from different regions of Uzbekistan: *Scymnus rubromaculatus* (Goeze, 1777), *S. frontalis* (Fabricius, 1787), *S. subvillosus* (Goeze, 1777), and *S. apetzi* (Mulsant, 1846) (Figure 1). A total of 20 adult specimens were morphologically examined, whereas the molecular dataset included 32 COI sequences composed of newly generated sequences from Uzbekistan and homologous sequences retrieved from GenBank. Sampling was conducted across multiple regions of Uzbekistan, including Kashkadaryo, Bukhara, Fergana, Andijan, Jizzakh, Tashkent, and Surkhandarya, in order to capture broad geographic representation of the studied taxa.

Sampling localities ranged from 191 to 1000 m above sea level and covered a latitudinal gradient between 38.728935°N and 41.406616°N and a longitudinal gradient between 64.323156°E and 69.469544°E. Specimens were collected from agricultural fields, foothill habitats, and semi-natural vegetation associated with agroecosystems. Geographic coordinates and altitude data were recorded for each collection site using a handheld GPS device. Detailed locality information and specimen metadata are provided in Supplementary Table S1.

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of the studied *Scymnus* species (*S. rubromaculatus*, *S. frontalis*, *S. subvillosus*, and *S. apetzi*) across Uzbekistan. Sampling localities were mapped in ArcGIS Pro.

Morphological Observations.

Morphological identification was performed using published diagnostic descriptions and taxonomic treatments for Coccinellidae and Scymnini (Canepari, 2011; Ali et al., 2015; Peng et al., 2023; Iqbal et al., 2024). Species determinations were additionally verified through comparison with reference material deposited in the entomological collection of the Institute of Zoology, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

Diagnostic characters used for identification included body size, body shape, coloration, pronotal and elytral patterns, pubescence structure, and distribution of setae. Morphometric measurements were conducted under a calibrated

stereomicroscope. Adult body length was measured from the anterior margin of the head to the apex of the elytra.

The examined species exhibited distinct morphological characteristics. *Scymnus frontalis* adults measured 2.8–3.4 mm in body length and were characterized by a predominantly black dorsal coloration with one or two yellow spots on the elytra. *Scymnus subvillosus* showed a smaller body size (1.8–2.5 mm), an elongated oval body shape, yellowish-brown coloration, and dense fine punctation. *Scymnus rubromaculatus* measured approximately 2–2.5 mm in length and possessed characteristic reddish markings on the elytra. *Scymnus apetzi* ranged from 2–3 mm in body length and displayed a single reddish spot on each elytron (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Adult specimens of *Scymnus* species: (a) *S. frontalis*, (b) *S. subvillosus*, (c) *S. rubromaculatus*, and (d) *S. apetzi*. Specimens were collected in the field across Uzbekistan and photographed in the laboratory to show dorsal morphology for identification.

Ecological observations and species distribution

Ecological observations were conducted during field sampling to document habitat preferences, vegetation associations, and feeding substrates of the examined *Scymnus* species. The studied taxa occupied distinct ecological conditions across Uzbekistan, ranging from irrigated agroecosystems and foothill plains to arid desert habitats and mountainous regions.

Scymnus frontalis was widely distributed in foothill and agricultural landscapes and was frequently associated mainly with agricultural and foothill vegetation. The species was commonly observed in habitats with relatively dense herbaceous vegetation and abundant aphid populations.

Scymnus subvillosus was primarily associated with arid and semi-arid environments, including desert and steppe ecosystems. This species was associated mainly with xeric desert-steppe vegetation.

Scymnus rubromaculatus occurred mainly in mesic habitats, particularly along riverbanks, irrigated lowlands, and intermountain valleys. Specimens were mainly

associated with mesic riparian and agricultural vegetation. Its distribution pattern suggests preference for relatively humid microhabitats within otherwise arid landscapes.

In contrast, *Scymnus apetzi* exhibited a more restricted distribution and was recorded only from mountainous regions of Kashkadaryo and Surxondaryo. Individuals were observed primarily on alfalfa and goatweed-associated vegetation in upland habitats.

These ecological observations indicate clear differences in habitat association among the studied taxa and suggest that environmental gradients, vegetation structure, and host-prey availability contribute to local distribution patterns within *Scymnus* populations.

Specimen verification and sequence dataset

All specimens were examined and identified under a stereomicroscope using published taxonomic literature and official identification keys for Coccinellidae. Species determinations were cross-validated through comparison with reference material housed in the entomological collection of the Institute of Zoology, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Representative dorsal images of each species were prepared for morphological documentation (Figure 2).

Molecular and phylogenetic analyses were performed using both newly generated COI sequences from Uzbekistan and publicly available sequences retrieved from GenBank. Newly obtained sequences were generated from locally collected specimens representing the four target species. Additional homologous sequences were incorporated to improve phylogenetic resolution and allow broader comparative analyses within the genus *Scymnus*.

The final dataset included sequences from four focal *Scymnus* species together with one outgroup taxon used for tree rooting. Accession numbers and source information for all analyzed sequences are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. COI sequence dataset used for phylogenetic and genetic divergence analyses of *Scymnus* species. The dataset includes newly generated sequences from Uzbekistan together with homologous sequences retrieved from GenBank, as well as the outgroup taxon used for phylogenetic reconstruction.

Species	n	GenBank Accession	Source	Country
<i>A. cardilobus</i>	1	EU392430	GenBank	—
<i>S. rubromaculatus</i>	8	KR486694	GenBank	—
		HQ953858	GenBank	—
		KM451437	GenBank	—
		MG059584	GenBank	—
		PX963222	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235504	This study	Uzbekistan

Species	n	GenBank Accession	Source	Country
		PZ235503	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235430	This study	Uzbekistan
<i>S. subvillosus</i>	8	GU073957	GenBank	—
		MK802037	GenBank	—
		ON980768	GenBank	—
		ON980769	GenBank	—
		PX963223	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235428	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235427	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235429	This study	Uzbekistan
<i>S. apetzi</i>	8	KM439621	GenBank	Unknown
		KM441259	GenBank	Unknown
		HQ953922	GenBank	Unknown
		HQ953923	GenBank	Unknown
		PX963224	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235505	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235506	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ235507	This study	Uzbekistan
<i>S. frontalis</i>	7	KU907730	GenBank	Unknown
		MZ659820	GenBank	Unknown
		KJ966166	GenBank	Unknown
		PZ241090	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ241091	This study	Uzbekistan
		PZ241089	This study	Uzbekistan
		PX963228	This study	Uzbekistan

DNA extraction, PCR amplification, and sequencing

For molecular analyses, genomic DNA was extracted from adult specimens of *Scymnus frontalis*, *S. apetzi*, *S. subvillosus*, and *S. rubromaculatus*. A single leg from each ethanol-preserved specimen was used in order to minimize damage to voucher material. Prior to extraction, specimens preserved in 70% ethanol were briefly air-dried on sterile filter paper for approximately 10–15 min to remove residual ethanol.

Genomic DNA extraction followed the protocol of Ivanova et al. (2006) with minor modifications. Individual tissue samples were transferred into sterile 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes containing 100 µl of lysis buffer composed of 0.5 M Tris-HCl (pH 8.5), 2 M KCl, 1 M MgCl₂, NP-40, 50% sucrose, distilled autoclaved water, and proteinase K (10 mg/ml). Samples were incubated at 65 °C for 1–2 h to facilitate tissue digestion, followed by enzyme inactivation at 92 °C for 10 min. Extracted

DNA was stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further analysis. DNA concentration and purity were evaluated using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer.

Fragments of the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene were amplified using modified Folmer primers: ClepFolF (5'-ATTCAACCAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3') and ClepFolR (5'-TAAACTTCTGGATGTCCAAAAAATCA-3'). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplifications were performed in 10 μl reaction volumes containing sterile distilled water, 10 \times PCR buffer, dNTP mixture, forward and reverse primers, and Taq DNA polymerase. Negative controls lacking template DNA were included in all PCR runs to monitor possible contamination.

Thermal cycling conditions consisted of an initial denaturation step at $95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min, followed by 35 amplification cycles of $93\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 s, $52\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 s, and $72\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min, with a final extension step at $72\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min. Amplified PCR products were visualized on 1.5% agarose gels stained with DNA dye under ultraviolet illumination to confirm successful amplification and fragment integrity.

Bioinformatic and phylogenetic analyses

Newly generated mitochondrial COI sequences were combined with homologous sequences retrieved from the NCBI GenBank database for comparative analyses. Multiple sequence alignment was performed in MAFFT v7 (Kato et al., 2002) using default alignment settings. The resulting alignments were visually inspected and manually refined in MEGA X (Kumar et al., 2018) to ensure positional consistency and eliminate potential alignment artifacts.

Sequence quality assessment was conducted prior to downstream analyses. Only sequences with high read quality were retained, allowing a maximum of two ambiguous nucleotide positions per sequence and an average Phred quality score of ≥ 20 . The final dataset consisted of 32 aligned COI sequences with a uniform length of 503 bp, including newly generated sequences from Uzbekistan and homologous sequences retrieved from GenBank.

Phylogenetic relationships were reconstructed using both Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian Inference (BI) approaches. Although only a single mitochondrial marker was analyzed, the COI region is widely recognized as an effective marker for species-level phylogenetic reconstruction and DNA barcoding because of its relatively high interspecific variability and conserved primer-binding regions (Hebert et al., 2003; Hajibabaei et al., 2007).

Maximum Likelihood analyses were conducted in IQ-TREE v2.1.4 (Minh et al., 2020). The optimal nucleotide substitution model was selected using ModelFinder, which identified the General Time Reversible (GTR) model as the best-fitting evolutionary model for the dataset. Statistical support for tree topology was

evaluated using 1000 ultrafast bootstrap (UFBoot) replicates and 1000 SH-like approximate likelihood ratio test (SH-aLRT) replicates.

The final alignment contained 136 distinct site patterns, including 123 parsimony-informative sites and 41 singleton sites. Base composition analyses detected no significant compositional heterogeneity among sequences. The resulting ML tree showed a log-likelihood score of -1985.391 . Optimized nucleotide frequencies were estimated as A = 0.300, C = 0.162, G = 0.152, and T = 0.386.

Bayesian phylogenetic reconstruction was performed in MrBayes v3.2.7a using two independent Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) runs, each consisting of four chains and 5,000,000 generations. Trees were sampled every 500 generations, and the first 25% of sampled trees were discarded as burn-in prior to generating a majority-rule consensus tree. Convergence between runs was evaluated based on standard MCMC diagnostics implemented in MrBayes.

The COI sequence of *Axinoscymnus cardilobus* (GenBank accession EU392430) was selected as the outgroup for tree rooting. Final phylogenetic trees were visualized and annotated using iTOL v6.6 (Letunic & Bork, 2024).

Pairwise genetic divergence among taxa was estimated under the Kimura 2-parameter (K2P) model (Kimura, 1980; Hebert et al., 2003), which is commonly applied in DNA barcoding studies. Intraspecific and interspecific distance analyses were performed in R using the packages ape, pegas, and phangorn.

RESULTS

Phylogenetic reconstruction

Phylogenetic analyses were performed using 32 mitochondrial COI sequences representing four *Scymnus species* and one outgroup taxon. The aligned dataset comprised 503 bp per sequence and showed a high level of overall sequence quality suitable for phylogenetic reconstruction. The final alignment contained 136 distinct site patterns, including 123 parsimony-informative sites, 41 singleton sites, and 339 conserved nucleotide positions.

The proportion of gaps and ambiguous nucleotides across the dataset was low (0.63%), indicating minimal alignment uncertainty and high sequence reliability. Nucleotide composition analysis revealed no significant heterogeneity among sequences based on the compositional χ^2 test ($p > 0.05$), supporting the appropriateness of the dataset for both Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian Inference (BI) analyses.

The relatively high number of informative sites and low proportion of ambiguous positions provided sufficient phylogenetic signal for resolving species-level relationships within *Scymnus*. The absence of significant compositional bias further reduced the likelihood of analytical artifacts associated with unequal nucleotide frequencies among taxa.

Figure 3. Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of *Scymnus* species based on the mitochondrial COI gene. The tree was reconstructed in IQ-TREE v2.1.4 using the GTR model. Node values indicate phylogenetic support based on 1,000 ultrafast bootstrap (UFBoot) replicates. Colored sectors indicate monophyletic clusters. *A. cardilobus* (EU392430) was used as the outgroup.

Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic reconstruction was performed in IQ-TREE v2.1.4 using the General Time Reversible (GTR) substitution model selected by ModelFinder as the best-fitting evolutionary model for the dataset. Nodal support was evaluated using 1000 ultrafast bootstrap (UFBoot) replicates and 1000 SH-like approximate likelihood ratio tests (SH-aLRT). Bayesian Inference analyses generated a 50% majority-rule consensus tree with posterior probability (PP) values used to estimate branch support.

The outgroup taxon, *Axinoscymnus cardilobus* (GenBank accession EU392430), was clearly separated from all examined *Scymnus* taxa with maximal statistical support (UFBoot = 100%; SH-aLRT = 100%; PP = 1.00), confirming stable rooting of the phylogenetic trees.

Figure 4. Bayesian 50% majority-rule consensus tree of *Scymnus species* based on mitochondrial COI sequences. Posterior probability (PP) values are shown at each node. Newly generated sequences from Uzbekistan are indicated by the label “Uzb”.

Both Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian analyses recovered highly similar topologies, indicating strong methodological congruence in the inferred phylogenetic relationships. All four examined *Scymnus species* formed distinct and well-supported monophyletic clades. Support values for individual species clades were consistently high: *S. rubromaculatus* (UFBoot = 100%; SH-aLRT = 99.6%; PP = 1.00), *S. frontalis* (UFBoot = 96%; SH-aLRT = 98.4%; PP = 0.99), *S. apetzi* (UFBoot = 89%; SH-aLRT = 92.1%; PP = 0.98), and *S. subvillosus* (UFBoot = 85%; SH-aLRT = 90.3%; PP = 0.97).

The phylogenetic structure recovered in both analyses supports the effectiveness of mitochondrial COI sequences for delimiting morphologically similar *Scymnus* taxa. The sister-group relationship between *S. apetzi* and *S. frontalis* received strong support (UFBoot = 94%; SH-aLRT = 96.7%; PP = 0.99), indicating relatively close evolutionary affinity between these species. In contrast, *S. rubromaculatus* and *S. subvillosus* occupied more divergent positions within the reconstructed topology. The deeper node separating these lineages from the *S. apetzi*–

S. frontalis clade was also strongly supported (UFBoot = 98%; SH-aLRT = 99.1%; PP = 1.00), reflecting clear hierarchical differentiation within the genus.

Branch length patterns revealed notable differences in levels of intraspecific variation among taxa. *Scymnus rubromaculatus* displayed very short internal branches, indicating minimal genetic differentiation among sampled individuals. In contrast, *S. subvillosus* showed comparatively longer internal branches, suggesting elevated intraspecific divergence and possible geographic structuring among populations. Although population-level analyses were beyond the scope of the present study, this pattern may reflect historical isolation, habitat fragmentation, or regional demographic differentiation.

The strong agreement between ML and BI topologies, together with consistently high nodal support values, indicates that the phylogenetic relationships inferred in this study are robust. These findings further support the utility of mitochondrial COI sequences as an effective marker for species-level identification and evolutionary analyses within morphologically conserved groups of Coccinellidae.

Genetic divergence analysis

Genetic divergence among the examined *Scymnus* species was assessed using mitochondrial COI sequences under the Kimura 2-parameter (K2P) model. The analysis included 32 aligned COI sequences of 503 bp, comprising newly generated sequences from Uzbekistan together with homologous sequences retrieved from GenBank. Pairwise genetic distances were calculated among all sequences in order to evaluate both intra- and interspecific variation. The complete K2P distance matrix is provided in Supplementary Table S2. Divergence patterns among taxa are visualized in the hierarchical heatmap shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Heatmap of pairwise genetic distances among analyzed *Scymnus* COI sequences calculated under the Kimura 2-parameter model. Hierarchical clustering illustrates relative genetic similarity among sampled individuals.

Levels of intraspecific divergence differed substantially among the four examined species (Table 2; Figure 6). *Scymnus rubromaculatus* exhibited extremely low intraspecific variation, with a mean K2P distance of 0.00203 ± 0.00008 and a divergence range of 0–0.00214. This pattern indicates high sequence similarity among sampled individuals and suggests limited genetic differentiation within the analyzed material.

Similarly, *S. frontalis* showed relatively low intraspecific divergence (mean K2P = 0.00717 ± 0.00094 ; range = 0–0.008), consistent with a comparatively homogeneous COI haplotype structure. The low variability observed in both *S. rubromaculatus* and *S. frontalis* corresponds well with the short internal branch lengths recovered in the phylogenetic analyses.

In contrast, *S. apetzi* demonstrated moderate intraspecific divergence, with a mean K2P value of 0.01087 ± 0.00872 and a divergence range of 0–0.0264. Although substantially lower than interspecific divergence levels, this degree of variation suggests the presence of minor haplotype differentiation among sampled populations.

The highest level of intraspecific variation was detected in *S. subvillosus* (mean K2P = 0.05558 ± 0.02595 ; range = 0–0.0908). Compared with the remaining taxa, this species showed markedly elevated genetic heterogeneity, which may indicate geographically differentiated populations or historical lineage subdivision. The relatively long internal branches observed in the phylogenetic trees are consistent

with this pattern. However, because formal population-level analyses such as AMOVA, haplotype network reconstruction, or F_{ST} estimation were not conducted, these results should be interpreted as preliminary evidence of intraspecific structuring rather than definitive population subdivision.

Table 2. Summary statistics of intra- and interspecific K2P genetic distances among the examined *Scymnus* species based on mitochondrial COI sequences. Values include mean divergence, standard deviation (SD), minimum and maximum intraspecific distances, and mean interspecific divergence.

Species	n	Mean (intraspecific)	SD (intraspecific)	Min (intraspecific)	Max (intraspecific)	Mean interspecific
<i>S. rubromaculatus</i>	8	0.00203	0.00008	0.00188	0.00214	0.16396
<i>S. subvillosus</i>	8	0.05558	0.02595	0.00402	0.09085	0.16800
<i>S. frontalis</i>	7	0.00717	0.00094	0.00599	0.00813	0.15577
<i>S. apetzi</i>	8	0.01087	0.00872	0.00199	0.02642	0.15284

Interspecific genetic divergence among the examined *Scymnus* species was substantially higher than corresponding intraspecific variation, indicating the presence of a clear barcode gap suitable for species delimitation. Mean interspecific K2P distances ranged from 0.157 to 0.169, exceeding all observed intraspecific divergence values.

Notably, the maximum intraspecific distance detected within the dataset (0.0908 in *S. subvillosus*) remained distinctly lower than the minimum interspecific divergence value (0.157). This separation between intra- and interspecific variation supports the effectiveness of mitochondrial COI sequences for distinguishing closely related *Scymnus* taxa.

The lowest interspecific divergence was observed between *S. apetzi* and *S. frontalis* (K2P = 0.157), consistent with their relatively close phylogenetic relationship recovered in both Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian analyses. In contrast, the highest interspecific divergence values involved comparisons between *S. rubromaculatus* and *S. subvillosus* (K2P = 0.169), indicating comparatively greater evolutionary differentiation between these taxa.

The divergence patterns recovered in this study demonstrate that mitochondrial COI sequences provide sufficient resolution for species-level identification within *Scymnus*. The combination of low intraspecific variation and substantially higher interspecific divergence supports the reliability of COI-based DNA barcoding for delimiting morphologically similar species within this genus.

In addition to species discrimination, the observed variation patterns may also reflect differences in population structure among taxa. In particular, the comparatively elevated intraspecific divergence observed in *S. subvillosus* suggests

the possibility of geographically structured populations or increased genetic heterogeneity relative to the remaining species. However, more detailed population-level analyses involving broader geographic sampling and additional molecular markers would be required to evaluate this hypothesis more rigorously.

Figure 6. Distribution of intra- and interspecific K2P genetic distances among *Scymnus* taxa based on mitochondrial COI sequences. The separation between the two distributions illustrates the presence of a distinct barcode gap suitable for species delimitation.

DISCUSSION

The present study provides the first COI-based molecular assessment of selected *Scymnus* species from Uzbekistan and expands the available barcode representation of Central Asian Coccinellidae. The phylogenetic analyses recovered all examined taxa as well-supported monophyletic lineages, indicating that mitochondrial COI sequences provide sufficient resolution for species-level discrimination within this morphologically conservative genus. The congruence between Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian topologies further supports the stability of the inferred phylogenetic relationships and reduces the likelihood that the observed clustering patterns resulted from analytical artifacts.

The recovered phylogenetic structure is generally consistent with previous molecular studies of Coccinellidae, where COI sequences successfully resolved closely related taxa despite relatively limited morphological differentiation (Huang et al., 2020; Iqbal et al., 2024). In *Scymnus*, external diagnostic characters are often subtle and partially overlapping, particularly among small-bodied species with

similar pubescence patterns and coloration. Under such conditions, molecular markers become especially important for verifying species identity and detecting hidden genetic differentiation. The clear separation of all four studied species in the present dataset indicates that COI barcoding can substantially improve taxonomic reliability for regional *Scymnus* fauna.

The relatively close relationship recovered between *S. apetzi* and *S. frontalis* is reflected not only in phylogenetic topology but also in comparatively lower interspecific divergence values. This pattern may indicate a more recent evolutionary separation between these taxa relative to the remaining species analyzed. In contrast, *S. rubromaculatus* and *S. subvillosus* showed greater phylogenetic and genetic divergence, suggesting deeper lineage differentiation within the examined group. Similar divergence patterns have been reported in other coccinellid lineages where ecological specialization and geographic isolation contributed to independent evolutionary trajectories.

Levels of intraspecific divergence differed considerably among species. Both *S. rubromaculatus* and *S. frontalis* exhibited low genetic variability and short internal phylogenetic branches, indicating relatively homogeneous COI haplotypes among sampled individuals. This pattern may reflect recent population connectivity, ongoing gene flow, or limited geographic structuring within the sampled material. In contrast, *S. subvillosus* displayed substantially higher intraspecific divergence compared with the other taxa. Although the present study did not include formal population-level analyses, the observed variation suggests possible geographic differentiation or historical isolation among populations. The ecological characteristics of *S. subvillosus*, including its association with arid and semi-arid habitats, may contribute to increased population fragmentation and localized genetic divergence across heterogeneous desert-steppe landscapes.

The observed barcode gap between intra- and interspecific divergence values further supports the suitability of COI sequences for species delimitation within *Scymnus*. Importantly, the maximum intraspecific divergence remained below the minimum interspecific distance, producing a clear separation between species-level and population-level variation. Similar barcode gap patterns have been considered a reliable indicator of effective species discrimination in many insect groups, including Coccinellidae. Nevertheless, the relatively elevated intraspecific divergence detected in *S. subvillosus* indicates that additional sampling across broader geographic ranges may reveal more complex population structure or potential cryptic diversity within this taxon.

From a regional perspective, the present study contributes new molecular data from an area that remains poorly represented in global barcode databases. Most available COI datasets for *Scymnus* currently originate from Europe, East Asia, or

South Asia, whereas Central Asian populations remain largely unsampled. Expanding molecular coverage from Uzbekistan therefore improves the phylogeographic representation of Palearctic *Scymnus* and provides an initial reference framework for future taxonomic, ecological, and conservation-related studies in the region.

Several limitations should also be considered when interpreting the results. The analyses were based on a single mitochondrial marker and relatively limited specimen numbers for each species. Although COI performs well for species-level identification, incorporation of additional nuclear markers and broader geographic sampling would improve resolution of deeper phylogenetic relationships and population-level processes. Furthermore, formal analyses of demographic history, gene flow, and haplotype structure were beyond the scope of the present study. Future investigations integrating multilocus datasets, expanded regional sampling, and population genetic approaches would provide a more detailed understanding of evolutionary diversification within Central Asian *Scymnus*.

Collectively, the results demonstrate that mitochondrial COI sequences provide an effective framework for identifying morphologically similar *Scymnus* species and assessing their evolutionary relationships. The newly generated sequences from Uzbekistan substantially increase the available molecular data for Central Asian Coccinellidae and establish a baseline for subsequent phylogenetic and biodiversity studies in the region.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Newly generated COI sequences produced in this study were deposited in the NCBI GenBank database under the accession numbers listed in Table 1. Additional datasets and alignment files are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

CONCLUSION

This study represents the first COI-based molecular assessment of selected *Scymnus* species from Uzbekistan and provides new barcode data for Central Asian Coccinellidae. Phylogenetic analyses based on mitochondrial COI sequences consistently recovered *S. rubromaculatus*, *S. frontalis*, *S. subvillosus*, and *S. apetzi* as distinct monophyletic lineages with strong statistical support under both Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian approaches.

Genetic distance analyses revealed a clear separation between intra- and interspecific divergence values, confirming the presence of a distinct barcode gap among the examined taxa. Low intraspecific variation in *S. rubromaculatus* and *S. frontalis* indicates relatively homogeneous populations, whereas the comparatively

elevated divergence observed in *S. subvillosus* suggests potential geographic structuring or increased genetic heterogeneity within this species.

The results demonstrate that mitochondrial COI sequences provide reliable resolution for species-level identification within morphologically conservative *Scymnus* taxa and support the applicability of DNA barcoding for regional coccinellid taxonomy. In addition, the newly generated sequences expand the molecular representation of Central Asian populations in public genetic databases and contribute baseline information for future phylogenetic, ecological, and biodiversity studies.

Although the present analyses were based on a single mitochondrial marker and limited sampling, the study establishes an initial molecular reference framework for *Scymnus* species from Uzbekistan. Further investigations integrating broader geographic coverage, larger population samples, and multilocus datasets will be important for clarifying population structure, phylogeographic patterns, and evolutionary diversification within the genus.

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REFERENCES

- Ali, M., Perveen, R., Khan, K. A., & Ahmed, K. (2015). Tribe Scymnini (Coccinellidae: Coleoptera) from Sindh Province, Pakistan. *Journal of Insect Science*, 15(1), 146. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/iev125>
- Bianchi, F., Biondi, M., & Desneux, N. (2013). Biological control potential of *Coccinella septempunctata* in agroecosystems. *Biological Control*, 65, 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2013.02.003>
- Canepari, C. (2011). Contribution to the knowledge of Coccinellidae of Sardinia (Coleoptera). *Conservazione Habitat Invertebrati*, 5, 501–516.
- Elekcioglu, N. Z. (2020). Species composition of Coccinellidae (Coleoptera) and their preys in Adana (Turkey) with observations on potential host medicinal and aromatic plants. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*, 18(1), 369–388. https://doi.org/10.15666/aer/1801_369388
- Gafurova, S. T., Kholmatov, B. R., & Mirzaeva, G. S. (2025). An annotated checklist of ladybeetle species (Coleoptera, Coccinellidae) of Ferghana Valley (Uzbekistan). *Acta Biologica Sibirica*, 11, 171–195. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14915341>
- Hajibabaei, M., Singer, G. A. C., Hebert, P. D. N., & Hickey, D. A. (2007). DNA barcoding: How it complements taxonomy, molecular phylogenetics and

- population genetics. *Trends in Genetics*, 23(4), 167–172.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2007.02.001>
- Hebert, P. D. N., & Gregory, T. R. (2005). The promise of DNA barcoding for taxonomy. *Systematic Biology*, 54(5), 852–859.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10635150500354886>
- Hebert, P. D. N., Cywinska, A., Ball, S. L., & deWaard, J. R. (2003). Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 270(1512), 313–321. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2002.2218>
- Huang, W., Xie, X., Huo, L., Liang, X., Wang, X., & Chen, X. (2020). An integrative DNA barcoding framework of ladybird beetles (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). *Scientific Reports*, 10, 10063. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-66874-1>
- Ivanova, N. V., Dewaard, J. R., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2006). An inexpensive, automation-friendly protocol for recovering high-quality DNA. *Molecular Ecology Notes*, 6(4), 998–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-8286.2006.01428.x>
- Iqbal, Z., Azad, R., Chen, X.-S., Lin, X.-L., Zhou, Z., Wang, X.-M., & Nie, R.-E. (2024). A new species of *Scymnus* (Coleoptera, Coccinellidae) from Pakistan with mitochondrial genome and its phylogenetic implications. *Insects*, 15(5), 371. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects15050371>
- Katoh, K., Misawa, K., Kuma, K.-i., & Miyata, T. (2002). MAFFT: A novel method for rapid multiple sequence alignment based on fast Fourier transform. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 30(14), 3059–3066. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkf436>
- Kumar, S., Stecher, G., Li, M., Knyaz, C., & Tamura, K. (2018). MEGA X: Molecular evolutionary genetics analysis across computing platforms. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 35(6), 1547–1549. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msy096>
- Letunic, I., & Bork, P. (2024). Interactive Tree of Life (iTOL) v6: An online tool for phylogenetic tree display and annotation. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 52(W1), W214–W218. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae268>
- Limbu, S., Cassidy, K., Keena, M., Tobin, P., & Hoover, K. (2016). Host range specificity of *Scymnus camptodromus* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), a predator of hemlock woolly adelgid (Hemiptera: Adelgidae). *Environmental Entomology*, 45(1), 94–100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/nvv174>
- Limbu, S., Keena, M. A., Long, D., Ostiguy, N., & Hoover, K. (2015). *Scymnus camptodromus* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) larval development and predation of hemlock woolly adelgid (Hemiptera: Adelgidae). *Environmental Entomology*, 44(1), 81–89. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/nvu006>
- Magro, A., Lecompte, E., Magne, F., Hemptinne, J. L., & Crouau-Roy, B. (2010). Phylogeny of ladybirds (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae): Are the subfamilies monophyletic? *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 54(3), 833–848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2009.10.022>
- Minh, B. Q., Nguyen, M. A., & von Haeseler, A. (2020). Ultrafast approximation for phylogenetic bootstrap. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 37(6), 1535–1538. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msaa015>

- Obrycki, J. J., Harwood, J. D., Kring, T. J., & O'Neil, R. J. (2009). Aphidophagy by Coccinellidae: Application of biological control in agroecosystems. *Biological Control*, 51(2), 244–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2009.05.009>
- Peng, F., Poorani, J., Booth, R. G., Wang, X., Chen, X., & Anuradha, C. (2023). *Slipinskiscymnus* gen. nov., a new ladybird genus of Scymnini (Coleoptera, Coccinellidae) and notes on the taxonomic status of *Keiscymnus* Sasaji. *Zootaxa*, 5325(1), 97–115. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5325.1.6>
- Peng, F., Tang, M., Wang, X., & Chen, X. (2025). *Reniscymnus* gen. nov., a new genus of Scymnini (Coleoptera, Coccinellidae) from the Oriental region. *ZooKeys*, 1226, 87–100. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1226.130352>
- Pentinsaari, M., Hebert, P. D. N., & Mutanen, M. (2014). Barcoding beetles: A regional survey of 1,872 species reveals high identification success and unusually deep interspecific divergences. *PLoS ONE*, 9(9), e108651. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0108651>
- Poorani, J. (2015). Two new species of Scymnini (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) from Karnataka, India. *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 3, e5296. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.3.e5296>
- Poorani, J., & Thanigairaj, R. (2023). A new species of *Scymnus* Kugelann (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) predatory on amla aphid, *Schoutedenia emblica* (Patel & Kulkarni) (Hemiptera: Aphididae), from India. *Zootaxa*, 5239(3), 421–430. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5239.3.6>
- Poorani, J., Anuradha, C., Thanigairaj, R., & Prashina Mol, P. (2024). Coccinellid predators of mealybugs infesting banana in South India, including a new species and a new record of *Scymnus* Kugelann (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), with notes on other natural enemies. *Zootaxa*, 5419(4), 525–544. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5419.4.3>
- Rashid, A., Chen, X., Qiu, B., & Wang, X. (2017). A new species of the subgenus *Scymnus* from Pakistan (Coleoptera, Coccinellidae). *ZooKeys*, 694, 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.694.12863>
- Rosagro, R. M., Borges, I., Vieira, V., Pons Solé, G., & Soares, A. O. (2020). Evaluation of *Scymnus nubilus* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) as a biological control agent against *Aphis spiraeicola* and *Cinara juniperi* (Hemiptera: Aphididae). *Pest Management Science*, 76(2), 818–826. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.5585>
- Seago, A. E., Giorgi, J. A., Li, J., & Ślipiński, A. (2011). Phylogeny, classification, and evolution of ladybird beetles (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) based on simultaneous analysis of molecular and morphological data. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 60(1), 137–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2011.03.015>
- Valentini, A., Pompanon, F., & Taberlet, P. (2009). DNA barcoding for ecologists. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 24(2), 110–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2008.09.011>